

Colourimetric Determination of Isoniazid in Formulations by Complexation with Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Picrates

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THE official compendia of isoniazid¹ (INH) describes iodometric and potentiometric titrations for its estimation. The involvement of the interaction of the drug with other compounds is also known². Various other reported methods include uv spectrophotometry, polarography and hplc in combination with rifampicin and thiacetazone³. Nickel(II) and copper(II) picrates form coloured chelates with isoniazid and exhibit maxima at 434 and 442 nm respectively.

INH (100 mg) was dissolved in methanol and made upto 100 ml with methanol. To each aliquot (0.5–3.0 ml) of the standard solution of INH (1 mg ml⁻¹) were added nickel(II)/copper(II) picrate (3 ml ; 1.0 mg ml⁻¹) and methanol (25 ml) and then heated on a water-bath for 5 min. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the volume made up to 100 ml with methanol. Absorbance of the resulting solution was measured in a Beckman 24 spectrophotometer against a methanol blank at 434 nm for the nickel(II) complex and 442 nm for the copper(II) complex and calibration curve was plotted against the respective drug concentration.

Powered tablet/capsule powder sample (equivalent to about 100 mg of INH) was dissolved in methanol (100 ml). To 1.5 ml of this solution were added solutions (3 ml each) of Ni^{II}/Cu^{II} picrate and methanol (25 ml) and then heated on a water-

bath for 5 min. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the volume made upto 100 ml with methanol. The absorbance was measured as described above and the amount of INH was calculated from calibration curve. The method was adopted in order to confirm its workability with the help four pharmaceutical formulations as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED AND OFFICIAL METHODS FOR ISONIAZID

Sl. no.	Formula- tion	Labelled INH (mg)	INH found (mg)		
			I.P. method	Proposed method*	
				Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
1.	Tablet	300.0	296.5	298.1 ± 0.1	297.8 ± 0.3
2.	Tablet	300.0	297.2	298.4 ± 0.3	297.4 ± 0.3
3.	Capsule	300.0	296.8	297.8 ± 0.5	298.1 ± 0.4
4.	Capsule	300.0	297.0	298.2 ± 0.3	297.6 ± 0.4

*Average of three determinations.

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